

Modeling the Triple-Star System TOI-568 Using EXOFASTv2

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ABSTRACT

We present observations from the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS), Tillinghast Reflector Echelle Spectrograph (TRES), and the Miniature Exoplanet Radial Velocity Array (MINERVA) of the false positive target TOI568 and provide best fit models for the data using EXOFASTv2. This object was labeled a TESS Object of Interest (TOI) by the mission due to the approximately 10-day transit observed; a secondary transit was also observed at around half of the period, suggesting a stellar companion around the host star. We spatially resolve two stars from AO imaging with a 0.29 arcsec separation, which corresponds to a minimum semimajor axis of approximately 140 AU given the stars' distance of 700 pc and their masses. Provided with the semi-major axis, we calculate that the secondary star has a minimum period of roughly 700 years, leading us to conclude that a third body is present in the system to cause the 10-day transit. The lack of any recognizable radial velocity perturbations in the MINERVA and TRES data from the primary star suggests that the transit event instead occurs around the secondary star. We then use EXOFASTv2 to produce fits for the transit light curve, spectral energy distribution, and MIST evolutionary models of the three stars. We derive the stars to be around 5.27, 2.7, and 1.99 solar masses and 6.4, 4.4, and 4.1 solar radii, with temperatures of around 13,900 K, 8360 K, and 6530 K. The MIST models constrain the stars to be young massive stars, and at least one appears to be past the turnoff on the main sequence. In addition, we found an unusually low rotational velocity on the primary star of 8 km/s, which is much lower than expected from a B star and likely indicates that we are observing the star pole-on. The massive triple-star architecture coupled with the pole-on orientation make this system quite an interesting and complicated target that takes advantage of several new capabilities from EXOFASTv2, which has never previously been utilized to model a triple-star system. The models and parameters derived from EXOFASTv2's fitting of this target serve as an excellent example of EXOFASTv2's capabilities as a flexible modeling tool for probing the characteristics of stellar and planetary systems.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the first exoplanetary candidate was confirmed in 1995 (Mayor & Queloz 1995), astronomers have confirmed thousands of exoplanet systems primarily through transit data and radial velocity observations. Other methods of detection — such as direct imaging, microlensing, and astronomy — can supplement the primarily short-period sensitivity of transits and radial velocity data, and will become more prominent as more data is obtained from current and near-future instruments. As detections increase and the quality of data improves, astronomers are better able to assess and understand a potential exoplanetary system — including ruling out the possibility of an exoplanet. Telescopes with means of exoplanet detection are equally capable of observing stellar systems, and the models and techniques used to model exoplanetary systems can similarly be applied to stellar companions to model properties and architecture of the system.

Understanding how to detect and determine whether a system is a false positive is useful to future exoplanet and stellar

research. For example, radial velocity perturbations that typically indicate an exoplanet exerting its gravitational force on the star can occasionally be created by stellar activity, causing radial velocity “jitter” that must be distinguished from radial velocity wobbles caused by another body (Luhn et al. 2020). Transits may also be falsely labeled exoplanets, when in reality they have a stellar origin. Understanding the architecture, properties, and evolution of complex stellar systems that arise from false positive candidates is equally important and fruitful for study.

Triple-star systems have also commonly been observed in these false positive systems. The first known triply-eclipsing triplet system was detected in 2011 (Carter et al. 2011) by Kepler and featured a eclipsing stellar hierarchical triple, with two-low mass stars eclipsing each other over a period of around 1.7 days and simultaneously orbiting a larger, more luminous star over a nearly 34-day period. Since then, Kepler has published around 5 triplet star systems as of 2013 (Carter et al. 2011; Derekas et al. 2011; Slawson & Doyle 2011) —

much less than the near 5000 discovered exoplanets. Yet a wealth of exoplanetary data is available to explore, and [Rapaport et al. \(2013\)](#) identified at least 39 additional plausible triplet candidates by applying an algorithm to Kepler data that inferred a third star from the eclipse timing variations.

In particular, the Transiting Exoplanet Survey Satellite (TESS) is used to characterize and study potential exoplanetary systems. TESS is a space telescope that searches for momentary dips in flux to find transiting planets. Already, TESS has confirmed nearly 300 planets and numerous other systems. When TESS finds an object being transited, it first labels the object a "threshold-crossing event" (TCE). Then, both automatic and manual vetting processes are applied to reject obvious false positives. The remaining list of objects become TESS Object of Interests (TOI). TESS provides a data validation report of its TOIs that includes a phase diagram of the transit, transit depth, and a difference image with out of transit centroid offsets. Additional extraction and analysis of TESS data, as well as corroboration with radial velocity data and modeling, is needed to confirm or rule out an exoplanet and reveal the characteristics of a system.

We can combine TESS data with radial velocity measurements to confirm the properties and architecture of a system. Typically, the depth of the transit gives the radius of the transiting object through the fraction of light it blocks while the amplitude of the radial velocity observations yields a mass. However, sophisticated modeling tools can estimate parameters for mass, radius, temperature, luminosity, and other parameters of the system. In particular, we model these parameters using EXOFASTv2, a IDL software for exoplanet modeling introduced in [Eastman \(2017\)](#).

EXOFASTv2 is a powerful modeling tool used to study and characterize stellar and planetary systems. The modeling is first initialized with several dozen parameters, which we provide in order to help the modeling begin in a reasonable place. EXOFASTv2 uses a Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithm to simultaneously characterize the parameters of the system and their uncertainties. In addition, new multi-star and linking capabilities have been recently introduced to EXOFASTv2 that enable more flexible modeling. Linking allows for the simultaneous modeling of stellar transits and stellar properties, since the "planet" can be linked to one of the stars modeled in the multi-star system. This linking lets EXOFASTv2 identify the transit as having a stellar origin and model diverse systems beyond planets. By determining the best fit model parameters and their uncertainties of a system, we can model the architecture and properties of that target with greater precision and contribute to the discovery of exoplanets and stellar systems in our Galaxy.

2. DATA SOURCES

Figure 1. Transit light curve from TESS of TOI-568, which shows a primary transit over around 10 days and a secondary eclipse.

Figure 2. Periodograms fit different periods to the MINERVA radial velocity data (along the x-axis), then measure how well that period matches the data on the y-axis.

2.1. Data Exploration

We began this project with the goal of studying a radial velocity target with MINERVA data. Initially, we looked at 24 datasets and created a periodogram for each dataset to determine whether any had a radial velocity wobble that warranted further study. We then selected five periodograms that appeared most compelling and followed up on the targets (Figure 2). HD217107, HD75732, and HD217014 were all confirmed exoplanets by [Fischer et al. \(1999\)](#), [Fischer et al. \(2008\)](#), and [Mayor & Queloz \(1995\)](#) respectively — in fact, HD217014 hosts 51 Pegasi b, the first exoplanet discovered in 1995. HD34411 and HD62613 did not have significant periodograms, with the former having more precise EXPRES data taken ([Zhao et al. 2021](#)) that does not align with MINERVA's radial velocity detections — suggesting its inaccuracy — while the latter was mentioned in a paper about stellar activity resembling radial velocity detections ([Morris et al. 2019](#)).

After determining that none of these candidates would be viable for study, we turned to MINERVA radial velocity follow-ups on TESS Objects of Interest. After looking into several targets, preliminary analysis of TOI-568 transit data posted to ExoFOP led us to initially conclude that the target was likely a false positive, but may yield interesting results on stellar systems.

Table 1. TOI-568 TESS Sector Data

Date Observed	Sector	Version	Exposure Time (seconds)
Feb. 2nd, 2019	S08	QLP	1800
Feb. 3rd, 2019	S08	SPOC	120
Feb. 3rd, 2019	S08	SPOC	1800
Feb. 9th, 2021	S35	QLP	600
Feb. 10th, 2021	S35	SPOC	120
Feb. 10th, 2021	S35	SPOC	600

2.2. TESS

TESS observed TOI-568 in Sector 8 between February 2nd and February 2rd, 2019 and Sector 35 between February 9th and February 10th, 2021. The TESS full frame images were obtained with a cadence of 30 minutes in S08 and 10 minutes in S35, but TOI-568 was also selected for 2-minute cadence observations in both sectors (Table 1). In subsequent sections, we describe our analysis of the 2-minute data.

We first extracted the light curve, which showed a clear transit at $P = 9.597$ days — the period listed in ExoFOP for TOI-568 — through the dip in flux, which was V-shaped. V-shaped transit curves are often generated when a large body orbiting at a high inclination barely grazes the host star, which may indicate a giant planet or stellar companion. We then inspected the TESS data validation report (Figure 1). Their phase diagram showed both a primary and secondary transit, implying a stellar companion. The centroid offset (Figure 3) does show that the source of the transit event is consistent with the primary star well within 1-sigma. However, because the TESS pixels are large, their flux blends together, making it impossible to distinguish around which star the transit occurs with TESS alone. The closest bound companions around the star are not resolved by Gaia photometry. However, the absence of a parallax measurement from Gaia DR3 is peculiar for such a bright star, and may very well be a circumstantial yet valuable indication that there is a secondary star present; Gaia reports no parallax and significant excess astrometric noise for this source, which often occurs when observations are contaminated by another component affecting the photocenter.

2.3. AO Imaging

Data from NIRC2, the near-infrared imager designed for Keck’s adaptive optics system with pixel scales of 10, 20, and 40 milliarcsecond/pixel, indicated the presence of a secondary star in the system. Using AO imaging from NIRC2 on Keck that was posted to ExoFOP, we resolve an image (Figure 6) of the stars in the K-band — both stars are visible, with a 0.29 arcsecond separation that corresponds to a

Figure 3. The difference image shows the offset from the centroid mass when light is blocked from the primary star. Because TESS’s pixels are large, there may still be unresolved stars near the primary.

semi-major axis of 140 AU, given the distance to the star of approximately 700 pc.

Figure 4. AO image from January 8th, 2020 at 562 nm and 832 nm shows the two stars seen in Figure 6.

Additional AO imaging confirmed that TOI-568 is a bound system — Figure 4 and Figure 5, taken three years apart at 562 nm and 832 nm, both verify that both stars are present and reveal no discernible movement relative to each other —

Figure 5. AO image from February 4th, 2023 confirms that the stars are in a bound system, as no discernible movement can be seen.

consistent with what we would expect for a bound system with a minimum orbit of approximately 700 years.

2.4. TRES

The Tillinghast Reflector Echelle Spectrograph (TRES) is an optical spectrograph on the 1.5-meter Tillinghast telescope at the Fred Whipple Observatory in Arizona, with resolving power R 44,000. TRES yielded radial velocity observations that were not significant; the third velocity point was flawed and the first two did not show any radial velocity perturbations around the primary star.

Figure 6. AO image in the K-band that resolves the primary and secondary stars, with a distance in the sky of 0.29 arcsec corresponding to 140 AU.

TRES produced a Cross Correlation Function (CCF) of the primary star (Figure 7), which shows how well a combination

Figure 7. TRES average line profile shows a narrow line from primary star (indicating a low rotational velocity) and a broad shoulder, presumably from the massive companions.

of lines in the spectrum correlate with lines in another spectrum taken at a different time. The CCF of TOI-568 had very narrow emission lines that indicated low rotational velocity of around 8 km/s, in addition to a broad shoulder feature caused by the presence of massive companions in the spectra. However, the temperature of the star suggests that it is a B-star, which we would expect to observe a rotational velocity of at least 100 km/s. While there are several explanations for this much lower observed velocity, the most plausible reasoning is that we are viewing the star almost exactly pole-on. This pole-on orientation has also been observed in the star Vega, and similarly causes the projected rotational velocity of the star to be much lower than its true rotational velocity (Hurt et al. 2021).

2.5. MINERVA

MINERVA is a radial velocity array at the Fred Whipple Observatory in Arizona with photometry and high-resolution spectroscopy capabilities primarily used to detect and identify exoplanetary candidates (Swift et al. 2015; Wilson et al. 2019). We generated a periodogram (Figure 8) and phase diagram (Figure 9) from the MINERVA data to see how viable the primary star of this target was for hosting an exoplanet or transiting object. However, lack of any radial velocity variation in the TRES data had pretty much confirmed that the transit occurred around the secondary star; we would then expect MINERVA to find no radial velocity perturbations.

This ended up being the case; the periodogram shows no clear period, and the phase diagram, generated based on the 9.597-day period taken from ExoFOP, showed no clear radial velocity curve. The amplitude of the radial velocity perturbations expected from the secondary star's orbit of around 700 years was calculated and found to be around 50 m/s over 2 years — our instruments can only detect radial velocity sensitive to 200 m/s at a minimum, so we would expect not to see any radial velocity observations from this target.

Figure 8. Periodogram of TOI-568 yields no definitive short period, indicating that the transit does not occur around the primary star. A red dashed line at the period found for TOI-568 reveals no significant peak at that period in the radial velocity data for the primary star.

Figure 9. TOI-568 phase diagram similarly yields no significant data and suggests that the transit occurs instead around the secondary star. While there is a slightly suggestive signal observed, the curve from that signal has the opposite phase of the transit observed and would imply a negative mass — we can therefore rule out this signal as noise.

3. GLOBAL ANALYSIS

3.1. EXOFASTv2 Modeling

We use EXOFASTv2 to model the system and determine best-fit model parameters. EXOFASTv2 can take in both transit and radial velocity data, and will produce best fit models to this data as well as a spectral energy distribution of the star, which will indicate the star’s effective temperature, luminosity, and type, and MIST evolutionary models that constrain the age of the star and its mass. Together with these models, the entire system can be effectively characterized and measurements of the mass, radius, density, luminosity, temperature and age of the host star, inclination, eccentricity, and additional parameters can be obtained. After successfully determining the architecture of the system using the

TRES and MINERVA data, we then aim to model TOI-568 using EXOFASTv2 and extract the properties of the system.

With this complicated triple system, EXOFASTv2 required dozens of input parameters for the modeling to begin in a plausible place, but uses a Markov chain Monte Carlo algorithm to find the best fits for these parameters. The radial velocity data TOI-568 were insignificant since the transit was occurring around the secondary star instead of the primary star that dominated the spectra. We initially began the fitting with EXOFASTv2 by inputting 3 stars and 1 planet so that we could link the planet to the third star in the system in order for EXOFASTv2 could identify the stellar transit. We obtained a parallax value from Hipparcos (van Leeuwen 2007) as it was not available in any Gaia data release, metallicity values from ExoFOP, and estimated reasonable values for radius ratio, inclination, transit dilution, initial metallicities, distances, and extinctions. In addition, we constrained the ages of the three stars to be approximately the same.

Figure 10. The MIST model of the primary star constrains it to be a B star, with a temperature of around 13,900 K.

The fit proved to be more challenging, and while the starting values were tweaked by eye so that the models reflected the data well, the fit soon became entirely unreasonable past 5000 steps. We then adjusted the values more by removing the transit component and modeling only the three stars based on the spectral data from Gaia, producing a best-fit SED and MIST models to constrain properties of the stellar system. These observed properties were 2 to 2.5 solar masses, 2 to 3 solar radii, and roughly 9000 degrees K for the three stars.

Once the triplet star system had believable fits, we reintroduced the linking between transit data and star, but EXOFASTv2 still had difficulties fitting the system. We made several adjustments to the parameters to account for this complex system. The dilute parameter was introduced — since the flux from the two stars is blended, the transit dip we observe is diluted by the light from the primary star by a certain

Figure 11. The MIST model of the secondary star constrains it to be an A star, with a temperature of around 8360 K.

Figure 12. The MIST model of the tertiary star constrains it to be an A star, with a temperature of around 6530 K.

degree that needed to be specified, which we obtained from the relative brightness of the stars given in the SED. When no radial velocities are given, EXOFASTv2 also constrains the mass of a planet with the Chen and Kipping relation (Chen & Kipping 2017), which does not apply to stellar companions and had to be deactivated; the mass and radius relation between stars is already inferred by the MIST model.

The ratio between the tertiary star’s radius and the secondary star that it eclipses was near 1, since the two stars are almost equal in size, yet the dip in flux is quite low, suggesting that the tertiary star eclipses at a high degree of inclination (otherwise the star would block most of the light from the star it eclipses). After setting the ratio to 1, the inclination was adjusted by eye until the transit depth of the model matched the data. The thermal value, which typically

indicates the depth of the secondary eclipse, had to be made deeper to match the observed depth, given the dilution and grazing secondary eclipse. However, the thermal value provided was the thermal value observed in a secondary eclipse that has already been observed with such dilution and inclination. Thus the thermal value given to EXOFASTv2 needed to correspond to the depth that the secondary eclipse would have been if it were not diluted or grazing, which is much higher than the 350 ppm that TESS observed. The out of transit flux also had to be adjusted manually after the thermal value was changed, since the out of transit flux corresponds to the host star only, and a significant thermal term from the companion inflates the modeled baseline flux.

3.2. Results

After adjusting these models by hand and iterating over thousands of steps in 20 threads, preliminary results of the system TOI-568 were obtained. We preliminarily find the stars to be around solar masses of 5.27, 2.7, and 1.99, solar radii of 6.4, 4.4, and 4.1, and temperatures of around 13,900 K, 8360 K, and 6530 K. The masses suggest that the primary star is a B4 star (Figure 10), the secondary star is a B9 star (Figure 11), and its stellar companion (Figure 12) is an evolved A2 star in its red giant phase — hence the cooler temperature. See Figure 13 and Figure 14 for the transit and spectral energy distribution, respectively.

Figure 13. The period of the transit of the eclipsing binary was found by EXOFASTv2 to be around 9.5992 days.

After adjusting the thermal and inclination, the secondary eclipse was found — see Figure 12 for this eclipse. The secondary eclipse occurs an hour later than expected for a perfectly circular orbit, indicating some level of eccentricity, which the model found as $e = 0.0103$, with 3σ uncertainty.

See Table 2 for a complete list of all the parameters of the system.

Figure 14. The spectral energy distribution of the 3 stars was relatively well-constrained with data from Gaia, 2MASS, WISE, and AO Keck NIRC2. The three lines represent the modeled SED for the primary star, secondary star, tertiary stars, and their combined spectra. The lower panel is a graph of residuals and represents uncertainty — uncertainty values of 2 sigma are relatively trustworthy.

Figure 15. The tertiary star causes a secondary eclipse which occurs slightly after the halfway point in the period, suggesting a slight eccentricity.

Table 2. Median values and 68% confidence interval for TOI-568

Parameter	Units	Values		
Stellar Parameters:		A	B	C
M_*	Mass (M_\odot)	$5.27^{+0.48}_{-0.69}$	$2.70^{+0.33}_{-0.28}$	$1.99^{+0.19}_{-0.14}$
R_*	Radius (R_\odot)	$6.04^{+0.51}_{-0.65}$	$4.41^{+0.35}_{-0.31}$	4.15 ± 0.43
$R_{*,SED}$	Radius ¹ (R_\odot)	$6.02^{+0.53}_{-0.59}$	$4.40^{+0.39}_{-0.34}$	$4.13^{+0.50}_{-0.44}$
L_*	Luminosity (L_\odot)	1270^{+550}_{-510}	85^{+50}_{-33}	28^{+16}_{-11}
F_{Bol}	Bolometric Flux (cgs)	$3.4^{+1.3}_{-1.1} \times 10^{-8}$	$2.36^{+1.0}_{-0.80} \times 10^{-9}$	$7.8^{+4.0}_{-2.7} \times 10^{-10}$
ρ_*	Density (cgs)	$0.0322^{+0.015}_{-0.0066}$	$0.0447^{+0.0063}_{-0.0066}$	$0.040^{+0.015}_{-0.011}$
$\log g$	Surface gravity (cgs)	$3.581^{+0.12}_{-0.070}$	$3.583^{+0.032}_{-0.040}$	$3.502^{+0.096}_{-0.088}$

Table 2 continued

Table 2 (continued)

Parameter	Units	Values		
T_{eff}	Effective temperature (K)	13900^{+1500}_{-1600}	8360^{+780}_{-820}	6530^{+880}_{-740}
$T_{\text{eff,SED}}$	Effective temperature ¹ (K)	14000^{+1500}_{-1600}	8390^{+820}_{-890}	6560^{+860}_{-780}
[Fe/H]	Metallicity (dex)	0.21 ± 0.15	0.18 ± 0.15	$0.16^{+0.14}_{-0.16}$
[Fe/H] ₀	Initial Metallicity ²	$0.17^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$0.17^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$	$0.17^{+0.13}_{-0.15}$
Age	Age (Gyr)	$0.085^{+0.038}_{-0.019}$	$0.49^{+0.17}_{-0.13}$	$1.19^{+0.31}_{-0.28}$
EEP	Equal Evolutionary Phase ³	$397.3^{+7.6}_{-14}$	$399.0^{+3.9}_{-5.1}$	456^{+11}_{-10}
A_V	V-band extinction (mag)	$0.366^{+0.080}_{-0.12}$	$0.366^{+0.080}_{-0.12}$	$0.366^{+0.080}_{-0.12}$
σ_{SED}	SED photometry error scaling	$0.93^{+0.34}_{-0.23}$	—	—
ϖ	Parallax (mas)	$0.922^{+0.094}_{-0.069}$	$0.922^{+0.094}_{-0.069}$	$0.922^{+0.094}_{-0.069}$
d	Distance (pc)	1085^{+87}_{-100}	1085^{+87}_{-100}	1085^{+87}_{-100}
Star C Parameters:		b		
P	Period (days)	$9.599227^{+0.000056}_{-0.000055}$		
T_C	Time of conjunction ⁴ (BJD _{TDB})	$2458521.9135^{+0.0027}_{-0.0029}$		
T_T	Time of min proj sep ⁵ (BJD _{TDB})	$2458521.9125^{+0.0027}_{-0.0029}$		
T_0	Optimal conj time ⁶ (BJD _{TDB})	$2458857.8865^{+0.0019}_{-0.0021}$		
a	Semi-major axis (AU)	$0.1483^{+0.0039}_{-0.0043}$		
i	Inclination (Degrees)	$75.22^{+1.0}_{-0.89}$		
e	Eccentricity	$0.0103^{+0.0028}_{-0.0034}$		
ω_*	Arg of periastron (Degrees)	13^{+18}_{-13}		
τ_{circ}	Tidal circ timescale (Gyr)	$0.0069^{+0.0053}_{-0.0029}$		
K	RV semi-amplitude (m/s)	69100^{+4600}_{-4900}		
R_C/R_B	Ratio of star C to star B radii	$0.928^{+0.14}_{-0.096}$		
a/R_C	Semi-major axis in stellar radii	$7.23^{+0.40}_{-0.41}$		
δ	$(R_P/R_*)^2$	$0.86^{+0.27}_{-0.17}$		
δ_{TESS}	Transit depth in TESS (frac)	$0.0126^{+0.0020}_{-0.0018}$		
τ	In/egress transit duration (days)	$0.1413^{+0.0038}_{-0.0045}$		
T_{14}	Total transit duration (days)	$0.2826^{+0.0077}_{-0.0090}$		
T_{FWHM}	FWHM transit duration (days)	$0.1413^{+0.0038}_{-0.0045}$		
b	Transit impact parameter	$1.817^{+0.14}_{-0.094}$		
b_S	Eclipse impact parameter	$1.827^{+0.13}_{-0.090}$		
τ_S	In/egress eclipse duration (days)	$0.1367^{+0.0071}_{-0.0077}$		
$T_{S,14}$	Total eclipse duration (days)	$0.273^{+0.014}_{-0.015}$		
$T_{S,\text{FWHM}}$	FWHM eclipse duration (days)	$0.1367^{+0.0071}_{-0.0077}$		
ρ_P	Density (cgs)	$0.040^{+0.016}_{-0.011}$		
$\log g_P$	Surface gravity (cgs)	$3.501^{+0.099}_{-0.087}$		
Θ	Safronov Number	$5.68^{+0.95}_{-0.81}$		
$\langle F \rangle$	Incident Flux ($10^9 \text{ erg s}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)	$5.3^{+2.7}_{-1.9}$		
T_P	Time of Periastron (BJD _{TDB})	$2458519.90^{+0.47}_{-0.34}$		
T_S	Time of eclipse (BJD _{TDB})	$2458526.771^{+0.018}_{-0.022}$		
T_A	Time of asc node (BJD _{TDB})	$2458529.149^{+0.013}_{-0.015}$		

Table 2 continued

Table 2 (continued)

Parameter	Units	Values	
T_D	Time of desc node (BJD _{TDB})	2458524.335 ^{+0.012} _{-0.014}	
V_c/V_e	Scaled velocity	0.9978 ^{+0.0021} _{-0.0031}	
$((1-R_p/R_*)^2 - b^2)^{1/2}$	Transit chord	0.646 ^{+0.037} _{-0.036}	
$sign$	0.56 ^{+0.42} _{-0.35}	
$e \cos \omega_*$	0.0094 ^{+0.0028} _{-0.0036}	
$e \sin \omega_*$	0.0021 ^{+0.0031} _{-0.0021}	
M_C/M_B	Mass ratio	0.743 ^{+0.094} _{-0.100}	
d/R_*	Separation at mid transit	7.22 ^{+0.39} _{-0.42}	
P_T	A priori non-grazing transit prob ...	0.010 ^{+0.014} _{-0.019}	
$P_{T,G}$	A priori transit prob	0.270 ^{+0.014} _{-0.016}	
P_S	A priori non-grazing eclipse prob ..	0.010 ^{+0.014} _{-0.019}	
$P_{S,G}$	A priori eclipse prob	0.269 ^{+0.015} _{-0.017}	
Wavelength Parameters:		TESS	
u_1	linear limb-darkening coeff	0.191 ^{+0.039} _{-0.041}	
u_2	quadratic limb-darkening coeff	0.282 ^{+0.050} _{-0.043}	
A_T	Thermal emission from the planet (ppm)	59600 ⁺⁹⁶⁰⁰ ₋₇₆₀₀	
δ_S	Measured eclipse depth (ppm)	59600 ⁺⁹⁶⁰⁰ ₋₇₆₀₀	
Transit Parameters:		2019-02-03	2021-02-10
σ^2	Added Variance	2.324 ^{+0.054} _{-0.047} $\times 10^{-7}$	6.57 ^{+0.27} _{-0.26} $\times 10^{-8}$
A_D	Dilution from neighboring stars ...	0.868 ^{+0.018} _{-0.021}	0.868 ^{+0.018} _{-0.021}
F_0	Baseline flux	0.9921 ^{+0.0018} _{-0.0020}	0.9921 ^{+0.0018} _{-0.0020}

See Table 3 in [Eastman et al. \(2019\)](#) for a detailed description of all parameters

¹This value ignores the systematic error and is for reference only

²The metallicity of the star at birth

³Corresponds to static points in a star's evolutionary history. See §2 in [Dotter \(2016\)](#).

⁴Time of conjunction is commonly reported as the "transit time"

⁵Time of minimum projected separation is a more correct "transit time"

⁶Optimal time of conjunction minimizes the covariance between T_C and Period

⁷Assumes no albedo and perfect redistribution

4. DISCUSSION

The target TOI-568 proved to be compelling and fruitful for study in more ways than one. While initially assumed to be a stellar binary, the system's architecture was instead a rarer hierarchical triple star system. While such systems are not uncommon among stars, they have not been as extensively studied and their capability for modeling is less

explored than stellar binaries and exoplanet systems. The pole-on orientation of the primary star was an unexpected and unique feature of the system, as well as the presence of three massive stars.

The primary star's narrow lines indicate the pole-on orientation, yet the eclipsing pair had a measured orbital inclination of 75 degrees, indicating a misalignment between the primary spin and the orbit of the outer stars. We hope to further examine the architecture of the system and determine whether there is a plausible formation mechanism to explain

such orientation. One relevant phenomena to study with respect to this system is the Kozai-Lidov cycle, coined in 1961 and 1962 by Mikhail Lidov and Yoshihide Kozai to describe the motion of a binary system's orbit when a distant third body is present — the oscillatory effects of the orbit lead to a periodic exchange between eccentricity and inclination. Whether such a mechanism can be applied to this system is certainly worth investigating, especially given the slight (3σ significantly non-zero) eccentricity found in the current orbit of the eclipsing binary through the primary and secondary timing and duration. We also hope to more broadly compare the properties and architecture of this system with other triple systems or binary systems to see if TOI-568 is consistent with physical parameters and a formation history that we would expect.

EXOFASTv2 had also not previously been utilized for multi-star fits, and such capabilities were recently added. The success of this fit demonstrates the flexibility and feasibility of EXOFASTv2 to model many complex and diverse kinds of systems, not just exoplanets, and rule out false positive candidates with greater certainty.

After deriving these preliminary fits, further steps include continuing to run EXOFASTv2 to most accurately model the system and confirm key parameters. Specifically, the parameters used to fit the SED can be updated with Gaia's new data release. In addition, the eclipse depth of 60,000 ppm appears too large for the primary eclipse depth and the shallow dip in the secondary eclipse, so these parameters may need to be updated further with additional fits.

Another way to update the model would be to further constrain the ages, since the current parameters place the stars at different ages — 0.085, 0.49, and 1.19 Giga years respectively. The model could likely be constrained further to

tighten up the ages of the stars. However, if resulting runs find that the ages remain disparate, then more exotic possibilities for the system's evolutionary history and formation could be considered.

Once the system is fully modeled and the parameters obtained, a stellar isochrone map could be created, which represents the lifetime of stars of the same age but different masses. Such modeling would provide a more complete and comprehensive picture of the system and enable us to constrain these field stars almost as if it were a star cluster.

TOI-568 is an utterly fascinating hierarchical triple system with three massive stars and a unique pole-on orientation. Further analysis of its evolutionary history and orbital architecture based on the properties we obtained could yield interesting insights into the formation and evolution of TOI-568 and similar triple systems. In addition to its complexity, the target was incredibly challenging to model — especially since it had not been done before with EXOFASTv2 — but our success has shown that EXOFASTv2 is a powerful and flexible tool whose abilities extend beyond modeling exoplanetary systems.

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